

DARIAH-FI UX questionnaireDescription

The purpose of the following questionnaire is to assess your experience with the resources of the DARIAH-FI infrastructure.

It will take you about 5-10 minutes to answer the questionnaire.

The questionnaire is divided in five parts: (a) pre-questionnaire questions, (b) demographic questions, (c) close-ended assessment questions, (d) open-ended assessment questions and (e) post-questionnaire questions. For questions 8-12, which are based on the UEQ+ questionnaire (Schrepp and Thomaschewski, 2019), you will need to indicate your level of agreement with the individual terms. For example:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
slow						X		fast

With this assessment, you state that you consider the tool, dataset or workflow rather fast than slow.

This questionnaire was prepared by Sanna Kumpulainen, Anna Sendra Tuset, Elina Late, Jaakko Peltonen and Farid Alijani (Tampere University).

Thank you for taking the time to answer the questionnaire.

Privacy statement:

This questionnaire is prepared to be anonymous. We therefore ask you to answer the open-ended assessment questions accordingly (e.g., do not include a person's name). All your answers will be processed anonymously. If you have any questions about the questionnaire, please contact Sanna Kumpulainen (sanna.kumpulainen@tuni.fi) and Anna Sendra Tuset (anna.sendratuset@tuni.fi).

Pre-questionnaire questions

1. To which tool, dataset or workflow are you providing feedback for?

Please enter the name of the resource or resources you have used

Demographic questions

2. Which is your age group?

Choose one of the following answers

- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65 and older

3. What is your field of study (e.g., history, literature, etc.)?

4. Which is your career stage?

Choose one of the following answers

- Bachelor-level student
- Master-level student
- Doctoral researcher
- Postdoctoral researcher
- Assistant/Associate professor
- Full professor
- Other:

5. What is your previous experience with information and communication technologies? Please rate your level of proficiency of the following:

	1 Beginner	2 Elementary	3 Intermediate	4 Advanced	5 Proficiency	No answer
Email						
Search engines (e.g., Google)						
Processing software or similar (e.g., Microsoft Word)						
Editing software or similar (e.g., Adobe Photoshop)						
Any digital tool used in academic research (e.g., Gephi)						
Online services (e.g., online banking)						
Social media						

6. What is your previous experience with digital humanities and computational social sciences?

obstructive								supportive	
not secure								secure	
does not meet expectations								meets expectations	

11. I consider the possibility of using the tool, dataset or workflow as:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7		No answer
useless								useful	
not helpful								helpful	
not beneficial								beneficial	
not rewarding								rewarding	

12. In my opinion, the information and data provided by the tool, dataset or workflow are:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7		No answer
obsolete								up-to-date	
not interesting								interesting	
poorly prepared								well prepared	
incomprehensible								comprehensible	

13. In relation to the tool, dataset or workflow you used, how do you feel about the following aspects?

	Very unsatisfied	Unsatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very satisfied	No answer
Code and algorithms						
Availability of data and metadata						
Quality of data and metadata						
Documentation, including instructions about restrictions						
Functioning of the system						

Open-ended assessment questions

14. For what purpose did you choose the tool, dataset or workflow?

15. Why did you choose this specific tool, dataset or workflow?

16. What aspects did you like the most about the tool, dataset or workflow?

17. What aspects did you like the least about the tool, dataset or workflow?

18. How can the developers improve the tool, dataset or workflow?

Post-questionnaire questions

19. Is there anything you would like to share about the questionnaire itself?

Please indicate if you have any comments on topics like the clarity of the questions, etc.

End message

Thank you for completing the questionnaire. We really appreciate your feedback.

Disclaimer: This version of the questionnaire was created and updated in several phases between 2022-2023. A special version of the questionnaire was also administered via LimeSurvey during the DARIAH-FI Christmas Workshop held on 19 December 2023.